

Investigate the improvement in organizational performance through Soft element of Total Quality Management

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Abstract

The aim of study is to construct a model by focusing the effect of Soft TQM elements on the Performance of an organization. The focus would be to construct a model which relates the Soft TQM elements and organizational performance. The responses of Top management, executives and workers will be received using self-administered questionnaire and online surveys through Google Drive. The responses shall help to compute Soft TQM and Performance through their dimensions. Soft TQM enhances the performance of an organization. This research work shall help Managers, employees, policy makers, quality trainers for improving quality perspectives and identification of Soft TQM importance for increasing performance.

Key Words: Organizational performance, Soft TQM, TQM

Introduction:

In this competition world, each organization faces different challenges from its local and international competitors in terms of technology and customer needs. To overcome the challenges organizations adopted to follow Japanese methodology for productivity and profitability. The concept that derives from Japanese industry is Total Quality Management (TQM). Under this concept every employee in the organization takes interest in improving the profitability and services of the organization with mutual consent (Salman, 2010).

TQM plays a vital role in quality management. Due to globalization and more awareness in customers, the organizations has more concerned about the quality of products and needs of their customers which changed from time to time. Quality management is a technique to retain existing customers and make new customers on the basis of customer satisfaction and through quality enhancement.

Banking business depends upon customer satisfaction with the products introduced by the banks. This classifies the banks as a services entity. When customer interacts with the bank staff then their effective dealings convinced the customer to come back or to move to other competitors. Thus banks have adopted the TQM customer first strategy. People believe that the efficiency and productivity of organization can be enhanced to implement the TQM (Zhang, 2000). It is observed that those organizations which are more concerned about the quality management of their products and services takes a major part of market share than other companies (Deming, 1998). TQM is not a set rule as it may be changed with the scenarios (Brah, 1985). Workers interest, support and their understanding will lead to better implementation of TQM (Mann, 1995).

A leader is always associated with the better implementation of TQM. Leader guide a clear version and plan to the employees and employees put their efforts for achieving them. Through this achievement they can change the organizational stakeholder's behaviors (Kotter, 1995).

Statement of the problems

This study aims to examine the perception of TQM on organizational performance in private banking sector. It also investigates that how TQM can affect the organizational performance of banking sector.

Research objectives

The object of this study is to evaluate the implementation of TQM in relation with organizational performance of banking sector of Pakistan. The aim of this research is to increase performance through TQM in banking sector. The constituent of this research is Soft TQM. The objectives are

1- To examine that there is no direct relationship of Soft TQM on Organizational Performance in private banking sector of Pakistan.

2- To study that there is direct relationship between Soft TQM and Organizational Performance

Significance of the study

This study helps the bankers to improve their efficiency and effectiveness in their regular activities with the help of TQM. The operation activities and quality performance of banking employees can be improved in the light of this research. TQM may be effective tool for banking sector of Pakistan but still now senior officials are not convinced for this implementation.

Delimitation

This study is only applicable to banking industry. It may or may not be helpful in other organization. It is primary research to cover the soft and hard TQM factors in banking sector because the data is collected only from banking sector employees. Researchers tried to focus on three factors of soft TQM and three factors of hard TQM using the instrument developed by (Samson, 1999). The data tool generated better results in other studies too.

Research Hypothesis

After understand the research problem following hypothesis are generated to reach the final outcome of the study.

H0: Soft TQM has not impact on Organizational performance.

H1: Soft TQM has direct impact on Organizational performance.

Proposed Theoretical Framework

The proposed theoretical framework is developed to check the above research Hypothesis.

Figure 1:

Literature Review

Since 1980 people realized that quality plays an important role in their organizational performance. The quality products and services are less costly and are based for long term survival of the organization. Employees are careful about the quality of work to enhance the performance of the organization. Total quality management (TQM) is usually adopted all over the world. TQM is ongoing process that never ends (Zairi, 1994). TQM can provide better results if it is treated with respect to organization vision, relevant teams and effective measurement system (Zairi, 1994).

Some authors views that TQM is a theoretical basics which provides plan to improve the organizational performance. Its values have been followed by all sectors of the organization industry (Evans, 1995). TQM is long term goal strategy process rather than short term goal achievement (Garvin G., 1991). TQM implementation can be checked out to those organizations whose focus on quality management as compared to those who don't (Montes, 2003).

The performance of an organization through TQM can be increased into two ways. The first way is individual learning about the aspects of quality changes and second is the level of the learning of organization members. TQM is a supplement to increase the business performance for better productivity. TQM has two constituents Soft TQM and Hard TQM. I this study we discuss the relationship of Soft TQM with the organizational performance.

Soft TQM and Organizational performance

Quality management researches have proved that soft factors are positively linked up with organizational performance. In 1995 Flynn checked the relationships between eight dimensions of quality management and performance through path analysis and he found that management support, customer relationship, supplier relationship and people management are soft. In 1995 Powell checked the relationship between 12 factors of quality management and performance through bivariate correlation.

Studies have proved that quality management can be enhanced by increasing the knowledge and customer needs. Researchers used the model which is developed by (Samson, The relationship between total quality management and operational performance, 1999). The analysis result of 400 firms indicates that quality environment affects the organizational performance and customer focus is the most important factor (Terziovski, 2003). Soft TQM has four elements called people management, supplier relations, customer focus and shared vision (Rahman, 2005).

Managers can achieve their goals by learning the employees about the customer needs and market demands. Firm's managers can empower their employees to build a culture of quality improvement.

Firms should acknowledge that the training which they provided their employees can be helpful in implementing the quality management in their activities. In this thesis, Soft TQM is computed into three factors leadership, people management and customer focus. Soft TQM contributors are discussed in further detail as follow.

Leadership

A leader has the ability to implement the quality management for better improvement in the enhancement of productivity. Leadership is a relationship through which one individual impact the behaviors of other individuals (Mullins, 1996). There are many leadership styles. Some are prominent like democratic & autocratic (Lippitt, 1969), employees oriented and production oriented (Likert, 1961). Early researchers did not believe that a leader can adopt more than one style in different situations. Later on it has been observed that a leader can adopt different styles with the situations. The performance management leadership style was discovered which is reliable than the other leadership styles (Misumi, 1995).

In large companies senior management has no time to focus on leadership importance due to which they are unable to meet the targets of their organizational strategic goals (Zairi M. L., 1994). Leadership is important in the implementation of TQM because it gives source of proper orientation and origin of quality activities (Prajo, 2005). Top Management Leadership is also very essential for development because personal involvement of plant manager for quality improvement somehow encourages the employees for adoption and learning of better ways to produce much better products (Abdallah, 2013). Leadership influences the unwillingness mind to work of employees with willingness for the organization. It acts as a umbrella under which organization grow.

People Management

The point when we speak about people management, we mean a method to improve employees in an organization. In order to play a vital role in organizations, the HR strategies that make up people management may as well reflect, increase and help the organization business points and objectives. A strong relationship will be required between the organizational vision and senior executives. This relationship will guarantee that HR intervention can get to be a maker and not an inhibitor of competitive advantage (Gratton, 2003).

Organizational culture impact employees in their professional goal setting and encourages them to achieve their task in limited resources (Karimi, 2012). So people management can affect a lot of change in individual thinking style towards the implementation of TQM.

Customer Focus

Customer focus is the main factor that is directly proportional to the business opportunities, increasing productivity and business growth. It generates relationship between the company product and their consumers to provide the feedback about their quality standards, adopting new technologies, customers taste and future business growth plans. Customer focused organization takes a major part in the market share (Fornell, 1992). There are two types of customers.

- 1- Internal customers
- 2- External customers

Internal customers are the employees of the organization whereas external customers are those for which organization provides services and they are from outside the organization. Customer satisfaction expresses that there is decline in complaints of the customers, more loyal feelings and higher customer retention but it is only possible if organization has direct focus on customers' desires and requirements.

Research Methodology

Research design and Tools

This is cross sectional quantitative study and structured quantitative techniques like Reliability, Correlation and Regression. The data collected from bank employees through an instrument, "The relationship between total quality management practices and operational performance" developed by (Samson, 1999). There are six questions in Leadership, Seven questions are from people management, and customer focus has six questions and seven questions from organizational performance.

Sampling Methodology

The population area of this research is private banking sector employees of Pakistan. 263 questionnaires are distributed through convenient sampling techniques. The reason of this technique is that it is locally available, less costly and less time taking. 243 questionnaires are received with the respondent rate of 92.39%. 213 questionnaires are selected for data analysis. The details are

Table 1:

Sr#	Bank Name	No of Respondents Taken
1	Allied Bank Ltd	42
2	United Bank Ltd	42
3	Muslim Commercial Bank Ltd	42
4	Habib Bank Ltd	42
5	Bank AL Habib Ltd	45
Total		213

The questionnaire is collected to employees and senior executives in banks on which they provide their responses. The sample size is taken close to those researches which have been taken before using same instrument. The SPSS 21 used for data analysis on the basis of 5 point Likert's scale which starts from 1=Strongly Disagree (SD) to 5= Strongly Agree(SA).

Reliability of Data

The data taken from questionnaire is entered in SPSS 21. For quantitative research it is most important to verify the reliability of that the data which we analysis are trust worthy or not.

The reliability of data is calculated through Cronobach's alpha which is considering the most important tool for reliability calculation (Pallant, 2005).

Reliability Statistics	
Cronobach's Alpha	No of Items
.918	45

The value of reliability is 0.918 which is above than 0.7, so scale is reliable with data sample. If the instrument is not reliable then data collected from the instrument is no more use because the results are not relevant.

Leadership

The value of reliability statistics for six items of Leadership is 0.670 which is close to 0.70. Hence it is treated reliable because the number of questions is less than 10 and the value of reliability is less than 0.70 in this case (Nunnally, 1978).

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
.670	6

People Management

The value of Cronobach's alpha is 0.698 which is very close to 0.70. It indicates that the reliability of these items is statistically good. The value of reliability is less because the items are less than 10 (Nunnally, 1978).

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
.698	7

Customer Focus

The reliability value for customer focus is 0.709 which is above than 0.70. This statistical value is quite good for further data analysis (Pallant, 2005).

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
.709	6

Organizational Performance

The results of the Organizational Performance are also more than 0.70 which shows the reliability of organizational performance.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronobach's Alpha	No of Items
.738	7

Soft TQM

Soft TQM computed of three factors Leadership, People Management and Customer Focus. The Cronobach's alpha value for these three factors is 0.697 which is close to 0.70. It indicates that 69.7% data to ensure the soft aspects of TQM are reliable. The reliability value is less than 0.70 because there is less than 10 items for soft TQM (Nunnally, 1978).

Reliability Statistics	
Cronobach's Alpha	No of Items
.697	3

Soft TQM and Organizational Performance

The overall reliability of all the constructs is 0.776 which is above 0.70. It shows the value of reliability is significant and can be used for further data analysis.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronobach's Alpha	No of Items
.776	3

Correlation

Correlation analysis is used to explain the strength of the linear relationship between two variables. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) value is found between -1 to +1. The positive value of coefficient shows the positive relationship between the variables and vice versa. The positive sign shows that if there is increase in one variable then there is increase in other variable with directly proportionality. Cohen, 1988 suggests the following guidelines:

Weak relationship $r = 0.10$ to 0.29

Moderate relationship $r = 0.30$ to 0.49

Strong relationship $r = 0.50$ to 1.0

Research table shows that the data is statistically acceptable. There is 2-tailed relationship which indicates that there are two dimension relationships between variables with statistically significance of 0.01 but in people management and information analysis the relationship is significant up to 0.05.

Coefficient

	Leadership	People Management	Customer Focus	Soft TQM
Leadership				
People Management	.340			
Customer focus	.407	.546		
Soft TQM	.474	.653	.500	
Planning	.319	.253	.339	.462
Process Management	.269	.163	.252	.338
Information Analysis	.353	.153	.276	.397
Organization Performance	.387	.295	.319	.498
Hard TQM	.410	.335	.348	.526
Product Hard-Soft TQM	.495	.571	.503	.868

There is direct correlation between soft TQM and organizational performance because the correlation value between them is 0.498.

There is direct relationship between organizational performance and people management but the relationship is low at significant level of 0.01. Soft TQM customer focus has direct relationship with organizational performance.

Regression (Soft TQM)

The regression test is run to check the linear relationship between the variables. The value of R lies between (-1 & +1). If R is close to +1 then there is strong positive linear correlation and vice versa. In table R=0.713 which shows the correlation between predictors (Customer focus, Leadership and people management) and Soft TQM. The value of R₂ in the table is 0.509 which shows that the predictors put 50.9% value for the Soft TQM.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sts. Error of the Estimate
1	.713	.509	.502	.82343

a. Predictors: (Constant)

ANOVA

This test is performed to check the variances of each item in the data. In the following table at p<0.001 the value of F=72.154, which shows that regression model is fit to predict the soft TQM.

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	146.769	3	48.923	72.154	.000 ^b
Residual	141.710	209	.678		
Total	288.479	212			

a . Dependent Variables : Soft TQM

b . Predictors (Constant), Customer Focus, Leadership, People Management

Coefficient

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.409	.201		2.036	.043
Leadership	.288	.061	.254	4.733	.000
People_Management	.474	.056	.500	8.530	.000
Customer_Focus	.111	.054	.123	2.046	.042

a. Dependent Variable: Soft_TQM

The result shows that if there is one unit change in leadership then there is 0.288 times change in Soft TQM. Similarly if one unit changes in people management and customer focus then there is 0.47 & .111 change in soft TQM respectively.

Regression (Soft TQM to Organizational Performance)

When regression is run, then a table of Model Summary is produced in the output. In model summary Table R=0.498 shows the moderate relationship between the Soft TQM and Organizational Performance. The value of R² represents that soft TQM plays a role of 24.8% of organizational performance as outcome. Hence it is proved that

H1. Soft TQM have direct impact on Organizational Performance.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sts. Error of the Estimate
1	.498	.248	.244	1.04412

a. Predictor (Constant), Soft TQM

In ANOVA table shows that at P<0.001 the value of F=69.609, which indicates that regression model is significantly predict the overall model for organizational performance.

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	75.886	1	75.886	69.608	.000 ^b
Residual	230.030	211	1.090		
Total	305.915	212			

a. Dependent Variable: Org. Performance

Soft TQM has direct impact on organizational performance. A table show that if there is one unit change in soft TQM then there is 0.513 times change in org. performance. The strength of this impact is strong at 0.513 (Cohen, 1988)

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.587	.203		7.831	.000
Soft_TQM	.513	.061	.498	8.343	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organ_Performance

Conclusion

In banking sector of Pakistan TQM is important factor for continuous improvement in their business activities. Statistically it is proved that Soft factors like leadership, people management and customer focus increases the organizational performance. These aspects directly take part in quality implementation process. So the H1 hypothesis accepted that soft TQM has direct impact on org. performance because the correlation value between them is 0.498. The magnitude of the relationship is moderate but is directly proportional with a significant level of 0.01.

Recommendations

TQM is a methodology for getting excellence in production and services sector. There is still gap in literature regarding second aspect of TQM which is Hard TQM work in services sector. The researchers should put effort to explore more dimension of the quality for services sector. The research should be empirically performed to develop a new model to make a series of step for TQM implementation in Banking Sector of Pakistan. Operational activities must be performed in accordance with TQM standards TQM audits should be performed through in-house trained quality experts on time to time basis to keep system working efficiently and effectively.

Bibliography

- Abdallah, A. (2013). *The influence of Soft & Hard TQM practices on total productive maintenance in Jordanian Manufacturing Companies* (Vol. 8). International Journal of Business and management.
- Brah, S. L. (1985). *Relationship between TQM and performance of Singapore companies*. International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management.
- Deming, E. (1998).
- Evans, J. L. (1995). *The management and control of Quality*. New York West Publishing.
- Fornell, C. (1992). *A National customer Satisfaction Barometer: The Swedish Experience* (Vol. 56). Journal of Marketing.
- Gratton, L. T. (2003). *The three Dimensional people strategy: Putting Human Resources polices into action* (Vol. 17). The academy of management Executives.

- Karimi, Y. A. (2012). *The impact of organizational culture on the implementation of TQM: Empirical study in the Iranian Oil company* (Vol. 2). American journal of Industrial and Business management.
- Kotter, J. (1995). *What leaders really do*. Harvard Business Review.
- Likert, R. (1961). *New Pattern of management*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Lippitt, G. (1969). *Organizational Renewal*. New York, NY: Appleton Century Crofts.
- Mann, R. K. (1995). *Factors affecting the implementation and success of TQM* (Vol. 12). The International journal of quality and reliability management.
- Montes, F. J. (2003). *Factor affecting the relationship between total quality management and organizational performance* (Vol. 20). International Journal of Quality and reliability Management.
- Mullins, L. (1996). *Management and Organizational behavior*. London: Pitman Publishing.
- Nunnally, J. (1978). *Psychometric theory*.
- Pallant, J. (2005). *A step by step guide to data analysis using SPSS for windows*.
- Prajo, d. (2005). *The Comparative Analysis of TQM practices and Quality performance between manufacturing and service firms*. International journal of Service Industry Management.
- Rahman, S. B. (2005). *Soft TQM, Hard TQM and Organizational Performance* (Vol. 33). Omega.
- Salman, A.-S. R.-B. (2010). *The implementation of total quality management for the banking sector in Jordan* (Vol. 4(2)). Jordan journal of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering.
- Samson, D. T. (1999). *Journal of operation management*.
- Samson, D. T. (1999). *The relationship between total quality management and operational performance* (Vol. 11). *Journal of operation management*.
- Samson, D. T. (1999). *The relationship between total quality management practices and operational performance* (Vol. 17). *Journal of operations management*.
- Terziovski, M. P. (2003). *The longitudinal effect of the ISO 9000 certification process on business performance* (Vol. 146). *European Journal of Operational Research*.
- Zairi, M. L. (1994). *Does TQM impact on Bottom-Line Result?* (Vol. 6). *The TQM Magazine*.
- Zairi, M. L. (1994). *Does TQM impact on Bottom-Line Result?* (Vol. 6). *The TQM Magazine*.
- Zhang, Z. W. (2000). *An Instrument for measuring TQM implementation for Chinese manufacturing Companies*. International Journal of Quality and reliability amnagement.